

Cross-Platform Integration of Accessibility into XR

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About RECITE

Led by St. Cloud State University (SCSU), the Resource Collaborative for Immersive Technologies (RECITE) seeks to improve STEM technician education through the accelerated integration of cutting-edge extended reality technologies into technician classrooms.

The partners in the collaborative are:

- CA2VES (NSF ATE Center)
- CAST
- Clemson University
- EARTH (NSF ATE Center)
- Motlow State Community College (MSCC)
- Somerset Community College (SCC)

To learn more about the project, visit recitexr.org.

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Glossary of Key Terms

- **Accessibility:** The practice of designing technology so that all users, including those with disabilities, can use it effectively.
- **Augmented Reality (AR):** A type of XR where digital elements (like images or information) are overlaid on the real world, often viewed through devices like smartphones or smart glasses.
- **Bypass Function:** A feature that lets users skip difficult or time-sensitive tasks in an XR application.
- **Extended Reality (XR):** A broad term that includes VR, AR, and Mixed Reality (MR), covering all immersive digital experiences.
- **Haptic Feedback:** Vibrations or other physical feedback from a device to help users interact with an XR application.
- **Large Language Models (LLMs):** AI-powered language systems that improve XR applications by understanding and generating human-like text.
- **Navigation Scanning:** A feature that helps users move through an XR environment by highlighting objects and text.
- **Speech-to-Text (STT):** A technology that converts spoken words into written text, useful for users who are deaf or hard of hearing.
- **Text-to-Speech (TTS):** A feature that converts written text into spoken words, helping users with visual disabilities or reading difficulties.
- **Virtual Reality (VR):** A fully digital environment that users can interact with, typically through headsets and controllers.
- **User Experience (UX):** The overall experience a person has while using a digital product, focusing on ease of use and accessibility.
- **Walkability Simulation:** A feature that replicates real-world movement within an XR space, aiding users with mobility impairments.

Introduction

Ensuring that all users, including those with disabilities, can easily navigate XR environments is crucial for creating inclusive human-centered design. In the realm of XR (augmented reality and virtual reality), addressing the diverse needs and preferences of a range of potential users is essential. However, designing XR environments that seamlessly integrate various accessibility features remains complex.

To simplify this process, we have created this document to guide XR developers in the creation of accessible XR applications by incorporating a range of accessibility features. By adhering to XR accessibility guidelines, best practices, and state-of-the-art approaches, developers can enhance the interaction experience for all users, including those with disabilities. This document presents a baseline of best practices for accessibility guidance for XR development process, practices that can evolve with improvements in technology and feedback from practitioners. It synthesizes recommendations from several existing guidelines and best practice documents listed in the Further Reading section.

In an instructional context, the goals of a given immersive learning experience will determine which of these guidelines can be implemented without altering the fundamental nature of the experience. A certain level of challenge is essential for learning, but care should be taken to remove barriers that are irrelevant to the learning goal whenever possible.

Removing barriers to learning is the goal with the Universal Design for Learning (UDL) framework. UDL includes accessibility as an essential component of an inclusive learning experience, but it goes beyond it by addressing motivation and the need for a balance between support and challenge to help learners with a diversity of experiences, needs and preferences find an optimal learning experience. To learn more about UDL, [visit the CAST website](#).

Key Features

Accessibility in XR requires the creation of a flexible environment where all users can control their experience by providing them with various options for how to complete tasks and/or how to alter their XR environment to fit their needs or desires. XR accessibility requires a comprehensive solution, addressing the needs of all individuals. Some considerations include:

General Accessibility

XR applications should provide flexible environments where all users can control and tailor their experiences for their unique needs and preferences.

- **Reduced background details and audio.** Developers should provide users with the option to remove or reduce background visual and audio details that are not essential to the experience. This will allow users to better distinguish the most important information provided in the immersive experience. For example, users with visual impairments may

find it easier to identify key elements of an interface if a busy background is replaced with a simpler option.

- **Undo/redo functions.** XR applications should allow users to undo or redo actions they have made either as an error or because of imprecision. These functions will allow users to correct errors that otherwise would be irreversible and are especially helpful to improve the experience of users with physical, cognitive, visual or audio disabilities.
- **Reduced speed and flexible time limits.** App developers should allow users to reduce the speed of the app or to increase the time allotted for making decisions or completing challenges.
- **Bypass functions.** For XR experiences that include complex tasks, physical, or reflex challenges, adding a bypass function can allow users to skip challenging or timed experiences while still allowing them to make progress in the app.
- **Save progress.** The applications must not lose the user's data. All user saves/settings/downloads/content created within the app should persist throughout use of the application. XR platforms and applications should allow users to save their progress at any time to avoid the need to repeat challenging actions and to allow them to pick up where they left off on the experience if there is an unexpected interruption or if they need to take a break due to fatigue.

As with the more specific practices that follow, the goal of an immersive activity will determine which of these practices are implemented in each immersive experience. For example, an experience designed to expose students to potential careers may provide more opportunities for flexibility than one that is designed for assessment, where options such as undo/redo and bypass functions may not make as much sense.

Visual Accessibility

The application should provide clarity and direction to the user through a combination of visual, audio, and/or symbols.

- **Altering the size of objects, elements and text.** Allow users to make objects and elements larger or smaller, including change of fonts for more easily readable text. Also, allow users to change the color of text and the background.
- **Audio augmentation and text-to-speech.** These features are important to users with vision loss or users that cannot read text instructions, labels, or other written elements in the XR app. Text-to-speech is a feature already supported by many devices like computers, phones, tables, and more. XR developers need to build their XR app to natively support an existing TTS technology.
- **Color filters and symbols.** These XR features allow users to comprehend information in the app that is communicated by color. To enhance the interaction experience for users that cannot discern color, XR applications should allow users to recolor the interface or provide shapes or symbols alongside meaningful colors. Another feature is to provide textures on objects or elements to help distinguish information in the application. For

example, using a scrim (a translucent gradient layer) helps in making text more readable against background pictures, colors, and other elements that can affect a user's ability to read it.

- **Alternative text for visual content.** For users with visual impairments, alternative text descriptions for images, videos, and 3D objects are essential. Also, applications should provide the user with the option to rotate their view without physically moving their head/neck and provide options for color blindness such as combining color and pattern for easy visual distinction.
- **Customizable text setting.** Developers can provide options for adjusting text size, font, and other visual aspects to accommodate users with varying visual needs. Text and in-app controls and elements essential for the application progression should be clearly labeled.

Audio and Language Accessibility

XR applications should provide more than one way for users to understand and control the audio features of XR platforms.

- **Captioning.** Providing captions or subtitles for audio features is one of the most common ways to make XR applications accessible to deaf and hard of hearing users. Also, XR developers should provide users the ability to choose where to place captions and to move them to ensure other visual aspects of the application are visible, ensuring a flexible environment where users can control their experiences.
- **Using icons to identify audio features.** XR applications can incorporate icons or other indicators to help users identify movements such as how they should move their heads or reorient their focus to ensure they are able to see the direction from which the audio is coming from.
- **Sign Language.** A universal XR application can improve user accessibility by providing an option to persistently display sign language interpretation within the application.
- **Language translation.** With a variety of cultures and languages, XR applications should provide real time language translation to fit the user's need or desire.

Mobility Accessibility

To improve access to XR applications for users with mobility and disabilities, applications should provide options to help them configure controller options.

- **Settings and Menu options.** A flexible XR environment should provide the option to configure usability preferences when initially setting up XR experiences, especially for those with mobility disabilities. Also, making it possible to save those preferences for future interactions enhances the interaction experiences for the user. Some settings and menu options can include setting the app to assist users in navigation of the interface and helping them to complete repetitive tasks. For example, a user may want to access the XR experience from a seated, reclining, or stationary position.

- **Automate actions.** All users can benefit by automating some actions to reduce the number of physical actions they must make within the application.
- **Map several actions.** Cross platform XR applications allow altering their environment to allow users to map several actions to a single controller button or action to complete complex multi-step actions within the application. Also, remapping of controls onto alternate controllers, sensors, or keyboards helps increase accessibility in XR applications.

Cognitive Accessibility

XR applications should provide on-demand functions, in-app prompts, and training to increase accessibility for all users, including those with cognitive and intellectual disabilities.

- **Provide on-demand functions.** XR application should provide on-demand functions to allow users to receive assistance in orienting themselves in the XR experience or to receive more information about their progress in the application and what to do next.
- **Provide in-app prompts.** These prompts can be reminders, introductions of new features, helpful topics, and others.
- **Provide training.** Training opportunities increase accessibility by allowing users to experiment with the interface and control configurations to learn difficult tasks they may encounter in the experience. Training will also allow users to familiarize themselves with the app and its interfaces so they can configure settings and preferences.

Multiple User Interaction Accessibility

XR applications should provide features that support multi-user accessibility

- Allow users to choose from various interaction methods (e.g., gestures, voice commands, controllers) based on their abilities.
- Provide navigation scanning to help users navigate the XR space effectively.
- Allow users to add contrast or edge enhancements to highlight objects and text.
- Incorporate voice commands for simple and frequent actions to enhance multi-user experiences.

By adopting these practices, developers can streamline the process of adjusting accessibility settings where all users can control and customize their experiences.

AI Enhancing XR Accessibility

Artificial Intelligence (AI) and **Extended Reality (XR)**, though originating from different fields, can be combined to create powerful tools to enhance XR accessibility. AI-driven dynamic content generation tailors XR experiences to individual users' preferences, behavior, and environmental conditions. This personalization fosters deeper engagement and enhances the overall user accessibility experience. Below are some ways AI contributes to XR accessibility.

Sensory Accessibility: Dynamic Adjustment, Speech-to-text and Text-to-speech.

- AI algorithms dynamically adjust screen colors, text size, and transparency in XR environments.
- For visually impaired users, AI highlights sharp contrasts in peripheral vision, improving picture quality.
- AI-powered speech-to-text provides subtitles for users who are deaf or hard of hearing.
- Text-to-speech offers audio descriptions, essential for those with visual disabilities.

Mobility Accessibility: Walkability Simulations

- XR features simulate movements like walking around a room, benefiting wheelchair users.
- AI-driven navigation allows hands-free interaction or voice control.

Inclusive Learning and Communication Accessibility: Personalized Learning Environments.

- AI adapts XR learning environments to individual needs and preferences.
- Speech recognition and synthesis facilitate communication for those with speech disabilities.

Language Translation and Interpretation Accessibility

- AI can automatically translate spoken and written text, facilitating mutual understanding between users who speak different languages.
- Large Language Models (LLMs) can understand context and generate human-like responses. Integrating LLMs into XR applications enables natural language interactions, making XR more user-friendly and inclusive.
- AI algorithms can adapt XR experiences based on user preferences, context, and language proficiency. For example, an XR application could adjust its interface language or provide localized content based on the user's location.

As XR technology evolves, practices will need to continue to adapt and expand. The integration of AI and XR opens exciting possibilities for creating more engaging, personalized, and accessible experiences for all users.

Further Reading

For more detailed guidance on the design of accessible XR experiences, we recommend exploring the following resources:

- [Chapter 3 of the XR Association's Developer's Guide](#)
- [Meta Accessibility VRCs](#)
- [XR Accessibility User Requirements](#) (W3C Draft)
- [XRAccess Community](#)
- [BBC XR Barriers Research](#)